

PSYCHOGENIC PAIN DISORDER

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ABSTRACT

This article addresses the topic of 'psychogenic pain disorder'. Its scientific relevance lies in the fact that it sheds light on this type of pain that apparently has completely psychological symptoms and that, for this reason, ends up being treated by doctors as false or virtual in nature, which is not justified because those who suffer from this illness experience very real sensations of pain. Its social relevance lies in the aspect of presenting the population with scientific elements that clarify that not every type of pain that cannot be diagnosed by a doctor is unreal and, in doing so, attempts to denigrate the person of the patient. This is a bibliographical, factual research, based on classical studies and authors on the subject. The objective is to deepen the studies on this type of personal suffering that affects a good portion of the population. Psychogenic pain can be defined as a painful sensation that has no organic basis. It is any pain of entirely mental origin, and that is fixed in a part of the anatomy. There is an approach to the understanding that psychogenic pain disorder is not a disease, a priori; rather, a warning regarding an unprecedented psychological conflict, the existence and persistence of which are unbearable to the individual, and, strangely, its clarification turns into a disease, because it reveals the presence of an etiological agent. Many studies still need to be carried out, with the aim of clarifying how human thought works and what mechanisms it uses to preserve and maintain the psychic economy, sometimes using subterfuges such as the mnemonic suppression of events that the individual could not bear in a conventional way; however, there comes a time when the brain demands the reestablishment of the order broken by the situation to be discovered, because it was suppressed for the sake of the patient's well-being.

Keywords: Psychogenic pain disorder. Mental disorders. Psychoanalysis.

INTRODUCTION

Psychogenic pain, also called *psychalgia* or *somatoform pain*, is pain caused, increased or prolonged by mental, emotional or behavioral factors. Unlike psychosomatic pain, in which

the thought is exposing an internal conflict using a body expression, as in the case of mourning, emotional loss, induced by social rejection, romantic disaffection, sadness, unhealthy love, or other events of an emotional nature; in psychogenic pain symptoms, the causes are so deeply rooted in the psychic system that even the patient ignores the *[possible]* origins of its cause.

Medicine also refers to *psychogenic pain* or *psychalgia* as a form of chronic pain under the name of *persistent somatoform pain disorder*. The causes may be linked to *stress*, emotional conflicts, psychosocial problems or psychological disorders. Some experts believe that chronic psychogenic pain exists as a protective distraction to keep dangerous emotions repressed, such as explicit anger or unconscious rage. It is quite plausible to imagine that, in the presence of an egodystonic person, in whom there is a conflict happening unconsciously and which the individual understands that he or she is incapable of facing it, not allowing it to become conscious, the internal battle tends to awaken such nervous reactions, which make explicit the need for some kind of escape valve, highlighting bodily pains in unexpected regions, as they do not present any type of causal link.

Patients are often stigmatized; medical professionals and the general public tend to think that pain of psychological origin is not real. However, experts believe that it is no less real or less painful than pain from other sources. There is no effective mechanism that can measure someone's pain; only the person who feels it can say how strong and able they are to tolerate it. However, it is important to remember that the emotional state tends to influence this support condition; it is not a situation that can be prescribed or indicated by someone else. Psychotherapeutic treatment helps the patient to seek out the tangible and intangible elements that, in some way, consciously or unconsciously, are causing and leading to this situation (Langley & Cheraskin, 2010).

The problem of how to face the situation presented by the patient is a challenge that transcends the psychotherapist's own action, precisely because having to advance in an affective-emotional space that, even despite the signs already given by the unconscious that there is a traumatic condition that is *demanding* to be clarified, the dimension of the individual's power in being able to face a situation that, for him, was until then unknown is, in the same proportion, an unknown to the doctor and/or therapist.

The aim of the exams and tests, cognitive interviews, the latter being the form that comes closest to proving effective in discovering the cause of the somatoform pain disorder, is to run into the problem that all the unconscious psychological material that has been repressed by the brain, as a way of protecting the individual's physical and moral integrity, reveals itself as an eruption of a dormant volcano, causing conflict situations that prove [*almost*] impossible to

resolve. Thus, faced with such a confrontation, the doctor and/or therapist find themselves in the position of using palliative medications, more powerful analgesics; not because they do not have the technical conditions to provide a state of cure to the patients; but because they know that they are facing a phenomenon that goes beyond the limits of the technical and empirical knowledge that they have and that, strange as it may seem, it is not the body that is communicating the trauma suffered; it is another instance, more powerful and more complex and that, strange as the statement made here may be, is anthropomorphic; therefore, it must be analyzed based on an interpretation defined in this way, *a priori* .

The human unconscious is an instance that, with due exception to the negative credits that common sense and ignorance, together with the contempt for Freudian Psychoanalysis, have instilled in it, its interest in mental health is the search for balance and harmony between the human being and his or her self in an integral way. For some reason, if this is not possible, caused by some conflicting and traumatic situation, it, upon understanding that the individual already has the conditions to face the situation, with a certain power or that the crisis is unsustainable and may lead to a tragic outcome, sends empirical signals to those around him, because there may be no imminent risk of his or her perishing; however, it has already been demonstrated that the patient needs specialized help, at least to preserve his or her existence and/or part of his or her sanity, not getting lost in the realm of alienation in which he or she may remain fixed forever.

Interpreted in this way, we come closer to understanding that psychogenic pain disorder is not a disease, *a priori* ; rather, it is a warning regarding an unprecedented psychological conflict and that its existence and persistence are unbearable for the individual and, strangely, its clarification turns into a disease, because it reveals the presence of an etiological agent.

ABOUT PSYCHOGENIC PAIN DISORDER

The DSM-IV refers to *psychogenic pain as Pain Disorder* . This disorder is diagnosed when the patient is concerned about pain, but no organic disease or pathophysiological mechanism is discovered after an adequate evaluation or, when there is an organic disease, the complaint of pain or resulting social or occupational impairment is extremely excessive in relation to what would be expected. Frequently, a temporal relationship can be established between an environmental stimulus associated with psychological conflict and an exacerbation of pain. Despite extensive medical evaluations, many of these individuals persist in seeking medical attention; some insist on surgical cures. Requests for disability certificates and

analgesics are common; chemical dependency often occurs. In the management of these patients, it is important to investigate and treat depression. Tricyclic antidepressants occasionally improve symptoms, even when the patient does not meet the criteria for a major depressive episode (TRIBIOLI, 2003).

Classifying psychogenic pain as a *pain disorder* is somewhat naive, because pain itself is already an alteration of normality, so if it is considered an abnormality, it must be taken into account that feeling pain is something normal. It could be considered that the nerve endings will conduct such sensations to the capture centers and emit a response as a mechanism that collaborates in the reduction and/or cessation of discomfort, but, in general terms, the classification given by the DSM-IV is obtuse and, in many cases, without semantic foundations.

According to what is discussed in the medical and psychotherapeutic literature, the use of medications indicated for the treatment of depression leads to thinking about a conflict caused by an ego-dystonic individual and the suppression of the production of certain hormones can lead to mood training and nothing more, allowing the conflict to be minimized by the state of pharmacological admonition caused by tranquilizers and other psychotropic drugs, which does not reveal the end of the evil nor the control of its root cause.

Etymologically, “psychogenic pain would be that in which, at its origin, the psychic stimulus would be responsible for its elicitation. However, theoretically and practically, the concept of psychogenic pain should not be translated according to this principle alone. There is a need for objective conceptual distinction for its better understanding” (FREUD, 2006, *sp*).

Sigmund is seen taking great care to say that the *psychological epithet* added to certain behavioral expressions refers to the *unknown*, in the most polite way of expressing oneself, and an authentic *I don't know*, in which the professional's ignorance regarding the problem posed is evident. As a psychotherapist, he would always seek the answers to these confrontation situations in the unconscious, trying to dialogue with it until he found the psychic roots and the somatic pathways that led it to where the clinical symptoms manifest.

Because of their organic expression, patients generally seek out a specialist doctor, confident that they already know, in advance, that their problem can be solved by that specific professional; when, after the preliminary consultation, they should be referred to a psychotherapist, so that together they can attempt a cure. This depends on the expertise of the doctor on duty and the amnesia that the patient undergoes during the consultation. How traumas manifest themselves or seek to reveal themselves to the patient is a condition that no one can predict; the only thing that is known is that the search for a state of psycho-emotional balance

in humans is something that lies outside the field of consciousness, and that the latter is responsible for nothing more than the enjoyment of happiness provided by well-being.

Psychogenic pain can be defined as a painful sensation for which there is no known organic basis that is causing it. It is any pain that is entirely psychological in origin and that is fixed in a part of the anatomy. In many cases, it is a symptom of a latent neurosis that the patient can or prefers to ignore. The predominant characteristic of this disorder is that the patient reports feeling pain, but no probable organic cause that could be causing it is discovered. "The concept of psychogenic pain is not universally accepted, but it has been the subject of numerous studies and is widely used in texts on pain. When one hears the expression 'psychogenic pain', it is almost immediately associated with fictitious or simulated symptoms" (MERSKEY & BOGDUCK, 1994, *sp.*).

The arrogance with which the medical community dares to credit itself with determinism over everything that others feel or fail to feel, based on the ignorance of others about psychophysical phenomena, means that, when faced with situations in which they cannot find at least a plausible explanation, they already determine that it is false or non-existent, or even that the patients are seeking attention. The strange thing is that, when they say such a thing, they are not entirely wrong; it is necessary to clarify what the patient wants with such a state of attention, understanding that this desire is pathological, requiring the intervention of a professional who can, in fact, meet such a particular expectation.

To consider psychogenic pain as fictitious is to adopt the philosophy of *ex nihilo* , in which nothing comes from nothing and this is an abusive and unethical condition arising from someone who swore to treat the suffering of others with total deference and investigative treatment. No matter how much someone can simulate a situation of pain, their behavior would at some point give them away and an experienced professional would know how to ask them questions that would cast doubt on their pain. A very classic case is the stomach pains and headaches suffered by the German thinker Friedrich Nietzsche (1844-1900), in which, after consulting most specialists in various medical fields throughout Europe, no organic anomaly was found that could explain the etiology of his severe pain. This did not constitute proof or suspicion that he was staging his crises; it merely revealed that the medical knowledge of the time was insufficient to diagnose the cause of his illness.

It is important to clarify that pain is not a disease, it is a symptom, an organic expression revealing that something is not functioning as it should. When its origin or causal link with some problem cannot be found, the effect cannot be taken as a simulated cause for shady and bizarre purposes. In the same way, for physiologists, in whom all pain must necessarily be

linked to a detectable cause, claiming that it is a neuropathic causal expression is to lower the medical level to charlatanism, almost approaching it to witchcraft.

Knowledge about pain and its intensity is a complex area, because there are individuals who are more resistant to it, while others are more sensitive to it; however, if there is no palpable organic source, the alternative is to use a symptomatic treatment, determined by the neurological condition, that is, it is necessary to seek to calm the nervous system and its surroundings in such a way that it provides relief, in the hope that it can stop completely, with the aggravating factor that, being of psychological origin, another factor appears that proves to be an immense complicating factor, the fact that it is not known when or where *it may* manifest itself again.

This is not a cerebral pain, because if it were, it would be specifically in the head region, and what is known is that the brain controls the entire system that involves the organism and emotional-affective issues are not palpable and much less detectable without the application of very specific techniques, and at most it can be deduced that this is the case, if the patient refuses to declare that he feels something that could disturb his peaceful experience. There is also the situation in which even feeling psychogenic pain, the patient himself reveals that there is no kind of conflict disturbing his intrinsic world, considering what has already been expressed above, that everything was protected from his conscious memory, exactly because of the dimension of the trauma that occurred; but, a working hypothesis that can be put forward is around the age of the patients who present such clinical symptoms, if they are over 35 years old, a time when the Ego seeks to resolve its conflicts and escapes to the Dionysian world are no longer sufficient to make it find the balance required by its Ego to reach the ego-syntonic state, which Nietzsche called Apollonian.

This is a way to try to find the *leitmotiv* that allows for a treatment that helps those who are affected by this disorder. Medical literature does not always take this detail into account, which prevents a more in-depth analysis and the production of a robust hypothesis regarding the case. From this age onwards, dreams tend to be more enlightening about traumatic situations experienced in early childhood and even around the latency period, in which the unconscious takes care of protecting the conscious memory, so that the individual can live in relative tranquility and harmony.

The concept of psychogenesis thus refers to psychogeny, psychogenetics, and psychic origin. The existence of psychogenic pain is considered when no nociceptive or neuropathic mechanism can be identified and there are sufficient psychological symptoms to establish psychiatric criteria established in the DSM-IV classification. In practice, psychogenic pain is

understood as a diagnosis of exclusion and is very rare. Many authors consider it virtual, since even purely psychiatric pathologies are manifestations of organic and identifiable alterations, even if only biochemically. “The term 'psychogenic' presupposes that medical diagnosis is so perfect that all organic causes of pain can be detected. Unfortunately, we are far from such infallibility. All too often, the diagnosis of neurosis as the cause of pain hides our ignorance of many aspects of pain medicine” (Melzack, 1996, p. 1).

Melzack raises a discussion that hurts the ego of the medical community and that, over time, has become jargon, taking over the field of common sense, allowing explanations (sic) for a series of things for which there is still no scientific knowledge. The expression “*psychological*” has come to imply that the cause or causal link of the problem is unknown; not necessarily that it is of a psychic nature, in fact, which creates a paradox, because everything arises in the space of thought and spreads from its action on the body as a whole. Therefore, it should be made clear that, when it is stated to be non-psychic, it means that it is not of a neurotic nature, a product of neurasthenia that cannot manifest itself, because of repressions suffered in other times and that remain as insurmountable mnemonic legacies.

As much as one can defend the idea of resilience in relation to traumatic events, believing that once the situation has passed, everything returns to normal or, at least, the individual should do so, demonstrating his insurmountable strength and vitality, the problem lies in the fact that few know how resilience and its mechanical tests work in the steel industry. Once a piece is subjected to strenuous pressures, it returns to a state of normality that cannot be detected with the naked eye; but it never returns to how it was; a deviation remains and, in the same way, it is the case with the human species, in which, once a trauma has been suffered, its personality structure undergoes psychological changes that cannot be repaired, much less perceived, unless the individual is placed in a situation that provokes similar feelings.

Once again, considering that pain is not a disease, it is merely the expression of something that is not working perfectly; therefore, it can be understood as a voltage sensor that allows a deduction of the degree of this illness that disturbs the individual who is affected by the discomfort. Many expressions are taken from the fields of exact sciences, where the effects and results can be measured with extreme precision and, without knowing the details of the process, such concepts end up being applied in a distorted way in the field of human sciences, producing effective ideas and impactful phrases as if everything were taken as ready and finished. The human being is a structure of the highest complexity and nothing that refers to him or his processes can be interpreted as something capable of being understood, in and of itself.

Memory is a situation of extreme complexity in terms of its connection with pain; because its occurrence is not isolated from the whole and, when a memory of happy moments is triggered, along with it, memories of distressing moments also come and vice versa, that is, the feeling of pain can turn into a feeling of happiness, as this can become a true martyrdom. Therefore, if a mnemonic set awakens anguish and pain, a possible way to alleviate the unpleasant sensation is to lead the patient to think about something or some event that made him feel good in the sequence of the situation.

Individuals who have suffered psychological trauma at some point in their lives, especially in childhood, tend to become hypersensitive, and conflict situations leave them in a state of such fragility that, to those observing from a distance, what they describe in terms of pain and suffering seems exaggerated. However, in the same proportion, they are susceptible to becoming emotional and excited about situations of happiness to such an extent that they do not even seem to be the same people who, just a few moments ago, were devastated, desperate and plunged into a state of depression that arouses concern in everyone around them.

Psychogenic pain is a common symptom in people with emotional problems. Anxious patients are especially prone to body pain. Mental work and emotional effort often cause pain. "Emotional pain tends to be located in the head and trunk with prolonged and continuous duration. It remains constant during hours of prolonged wakefulness, without interfering with sleep" (LEWIS, 1998, *sp.*).

What can be inferred from this statement by the author is that those who suffer from emotional disorders are more prone to conflicts of an ego-dystonic nature, in which during the waking state the Superego acts by repressing the Ego, not allowing the individual to become exalted or to go beyond socially permitted limits, even if their careful education grants them the freedom to do so; thus, the only way to alleviate the conflicting tension that explodes within the being is by provoking extreme tension at some point.

The fact that this pain, in particular, does not disturb sleep is because during this state the psychic barriers are loosened and the Ego can resolve some conflicts, allowing itself to exalt itself or even move towards actions that, under other conditions, are not permitted by the moral sensor. If there is an extreme conflict between the Apollonian and the Dionysian states, in which the desire to achieve the former can only be achieved through the latter; however, this is also prevented by some force superior to the individual himself, here is a constellation of extreme complexity, which cannot be resolved by a weakened ego, which leads the body itself to be the object of revelations of a problem for which the Id and the Ego demand a solution.

The most that can be achieved when attempting a dialectical connection with the unconscious is to deduce its interests in favor of the life and harmonious existence of the individual with the world that surrounds him. The language and forms of communication that this psychic instance uses to promote the treatment and solution of intimate problems remain an enigma to the scientific world and not even the Master of Vienna was able to clarify, leaving a special condition of understanding and possibilities for new studies.

There are also cases in which psychogenic pain is linked to punishments applied by the *Id* to individuals who dared to reveal secrets for which they were not properly prepared. Pope Pius XII clarified, in an event in 1953, that there are secrets, the product of traumatic events, that the brain keeps hidden from the patient because the patient does not have the psychological structure to withstand the pain caused by the violence suffered, even many years after the occurrence. Here is a maxim that the unconscious holds in high value, in order to preserve the life and serene existence of the being: *You will know the truth and it will kill you!* If it fails, I will not fail!

Very little is still known about the functioning of the human *psyche* and its mechanisms of defense and protection of life and individual well-being, precisely because this knowledge is due to linguistic expression, to individual, particular and singular language, and not everyone knows how to express what they actually feel and how they feel it, depending on the interpretations of third parties who have traumas and vicissitudes more or less violent than those of their patients, and this ends up creating a vicious circle that takes no one anywhere.

In psychogenic pain, there is a painful sensation that is effectively felt by the individual, but without any tangible reason to explain it, without a detectable organic cause. It is, therefore, a physical pain of psychic origin, and therefore its origin is based on a dysfunction of thought. Seeking to understand the psychic origins of this pain, Juan-David Nasio proposes 3 (three) possibilities, all of them anchored in the idea of a body endowed with memory:

In the first possibility, psychogenic pain would be the memory in the body of an old pain, the painful revival of a forgotten organic pain. In the second, as in the case of conversion, it would be the painful return to a specific part of the body, previously marked by the momentary presence of a drive that was soon repressed. In the third possibility, it would be the manifestation of a mere coincidence, which occurred in the past, between the momentary emergence of an unconscious drive that needed to be repressed, and a banal pain that fortuitously arose somewhere in the body, where psychogenic pain now appears. Psychogenic pain, moreover, can be of a hysterical or hypochondriacal nature. (...) in psychogenic pain, there is no precise location of the psychic pain in the body (Marinho, 2009, 212-213).

Some cases of psychogenic pain occur in response to a previous injury; in rare cases, the pain is caused purely by a psychological disorder. In most cases, however, psychogenic pain causes pain to be felt more intensely by some physical stimulus. Because the brain is the center for deciphering and localizing levels of discomfort, individuals with an underlying emotional disorder are at greater risk for experiencing psychogenic pain. Some patients present with persistent pain without evidence of any underlying medical condition. Many others present with a degree of pain and disability that is out of proportion to that of most individuals with a similar injury or illness. Psychological disorders are often responsible for at least some of these complaints. The pain experienced by the patient may be predominantly psychogenic in origin, or it may be caused by a physical disorder and exaggerated in degree and duration by psychological stress. Most commonly, pain of psychological origin is headache, back pain, facial pain, abdominal pain, or pelvic pain. The fact that the cause of pain is partially or totally of psychological origin does not mean that it is not real (Tribioli, 2003) .

In Psychology, this is an essential point of treatment; the idea of the existence of something already validates it as real, even if it cannot be measured, which is what the ideology of positivist thought assumes, in which everything must be capable of exact measurement in order to be defined as a fact. Dialogue with the patient is the only plausible path that can lead to satisfactory results with regard to psychogenic pain, analyzing the moment in which it manifests itself and under what conditions it does so, trying to understand which situations trigger the unknown and repressed traumatic process.

Sigmund, in his 1895 work on the origin of hysteria, reports that the manifestation of a traumatic feeling can occur from a co-relation with some object linked to the situation that provoked the traumatic event. This includes a list of sounds, voices, colors, situations, and music in which the memory is triggered and the individual's thoughts are taken to that fateful moment in his or her life. Generally, he or she will repeat the behavior adopted at that moment and, if his or her condition showed an intense fragility in the face of the aggressor, in which the only attitude he or she could experience was helplessness, this can transform into pain, resulting in the expression of the mnemonic weakness of his or her ego; the desire repressed by fear and the psychological violence of the situation against him or her; and the pain can also be a form of punishment against the member that could [*or should*] have been used to defend oneself or others.

From the outside, it is very difficult to interpret and evaluate the process as a whole, speaking on behalf of someone else; only psychological research, based on an in-depth anamnesis, led by competent professionals can allow a lucid diagnosis of the situation that

occurred and the individual behavior and diffuse feelings that crossed the individual's mind at the moment he was unexpectedly assaulted. Of course, expressed in this way, it may seem absurd, because if it were not for the element of surprise, there would be no production of psychological *trauma* , with negative long-term consequences.

ORIGINS OF PSYCHOGENIC PAIN

The fact that unconscious thinking produces psychogenic pain leads some professionals to believe that it is *all in the head* . However, because the symptoms of this type of pain are real and can seriously affect sufferers, all cases of this type of pain should be taken seriously and carefully investigated to identify the underlying psychological disorder responsible for producing psychogenic pain.

A pertinent observation regarding nonspecific (or psychogenic) pain is chest pain syndrome, which commonly occurs in individuals under the age of 50. These patients often present with symptoms that include chest pain, as well as radiating arm and neck pain. While in some patients these symptoms sound like warning signs of a heart attack, in most cases, chest pain syndrome arises from an underlying anxiety and/or panic disorder. As a result, treatment for these patients should revolve around treating the psychological disorder to prevent chest pain syndrome from recurring (Merskey and Bogduk, 1994).

This syndrome occurs because there is an abrupt constriction of venous blood, causing it to circulate at a greater speed and the heart to beat faster, at an accelerated rhythm, because it is receiving a much greater flow of blood than usual. It is necessary to discover the etiological agent that led to such a state of emotional tension. In this sense, the cause of such a situation is linked to emotional losses, such as mourning, death or unrequited love.

This does not mean that *every* expression of psychogenic pain has a passionate background, a deep feeling, although this condition cannot be denied in absolute terms, because the way in which each human being feels and expresses their conflicts, of any and all natures, is very unique, and there is no way to interpret them based on previously established averages. What is up to the analyst is to have the necessary knowledge to conduct the investigative process in the most intense way possible, allowing him to get as close as possible to an understanding, developing, from this, hypotheses that prove to be increasingly convincing and persistent until the meaning of the somatoform manifestation can be clarified.

Experts have come up with three theories that attempt to identify the causes of psychogenic pain, the first being that underlying psychological factors cause it. These include

anxiety disorder, bipolar disorder, depression, obsessive-compulsive behavior, and panic attacks. The second is that psychogenic pain results from a previous injury that has not yet fully healed. In this theory, emotional issues (but not the cause) induce pain and can intensify it if the underlying physical cause of the pain is not treated, and the third is based on the assumption that psychogenic pain causes existing pain to feel worse than the situation actually deserves. According to this theory, psychological issues can cause the patient to feel exaggerated pain that is more intense compared to the extent of the physical injury or illness. While their feelings of pain are real, the underlying mental disorder plays a role in intensifying the pain. Psychogenic pain generally causes the following symptoms: Constant discomfort despite taking medication; Difficulty describing the location, quality, and depth of the pain; Non-localized pain that encompasses larger parts of the body; Worsening of pain independent of any underlying medical condition (BYKOV *et al*, 1994).

Only after performing a series of tests (including MRI, CT scan, blood tests, *etc.*) will the doctor be able to rule out or diagnose the pain as psychogenic. Possible ways to alleviate physical pain include physical therapy, especially when muscles and joints are experiencing pain, making dietary changes, adhering to a healthy exercise regimen, and taking medication recommended by the specialist. After the physical pain has been treated, the patient is ready to seek out his or her therapists or psychiatrists to identify and work on his or her psychological disorder. Initially, the mental health specialists will build a psychological profile of factors in the patient's family history, personal medical history, and lifestyle habits and choices. Then, over a series of sessions, the patient and his or her specialist will attempt to identify the sources and triggers, as well as treatment strategies for his or her psychogenic pain (*Id.*).

While relieving the immediate physical pain is usually easy, treating the associated mental health disorder requires much more work. It should be noted that treating mental health disorders is often referred to as long-term management of medication and therapy. Without treatment, individuals suffering from psychogenic pain may experience negative lifestyle changes, including alcohol abuse, drug abuse, fatigue, irritability, isolation, sleep loss, and memory loss, the latter condition being a final way to prevent secrets, long hidden by the brain itself, from interfering with the state of life and existence.

It is not about eliminating the uncomfortable clinical symptoms caused by somatoform pain; the process is to find a solution to the cause of the problem that causes it, and for this, it is necessary to do an exhaustive search for the processes that the patient has gone through since childhood until the present moment. Regression therapies may well prove promising in order

to identify the traumatic event that became the trigger for the manifestation of pain, in the form of psychogenesis.

The authors reveal that the persistence of the expressed symptoms of pain and the lack of a cure for the problem can lead patients to acquire habits that are harmful to their health, such as addiction to drugs and/or medications that help to moderately alleviate the anxiety attacks, because that is how they end, affecting the mood and life as a whole, including the social aspect.

Each year, Psychology and Psychoanalysis have sought to deepen their field of study and knowledge about human thought, especially in order to clarify how the brain works to protect the individual from traumatic situations, with which it would not be able to live in harmony, and the effort to protect itself is sometimes insufficient, since human life was designed to be lived without violence that would harm the normal course developed and defined by *Physis*. Trauma is this, the result of a conflict so intense that the individual was unable to withstand the aggression and had, as the ultimate goal of preserving his life, to retreat and fix his thoughts on a certain moment, also becoming trapped in the traumatic situation, trying somehow to avoid it and, upon realizing that it would be impossible to do so, he obscures such memory, making it inaccessible. However, as Sigmund stated in 1909 at Clark University, it is not enough to lock the aggressor in a room and close the doors, because he will continue to pound on it, trying to make himself heard, which will continue to disturb the relative tranquility of those present in the room. Thus, one can come to the conclusion that psychogenic pain is the echoes of this unknown agent that has been banished from consciousness to unconsciousness; however, it continues to demand to be heard regarding its demands, because it is in search of an Apollonian state of being.

CONCLUSION

Pain of psychogenic origin is a metabolic disorder caused by an etiological agent unknown to conventional clinical medicine, *a priori*. Its origins can be traced back to an unconscious pathological state to which the individual no longer has access, for reasons unknown even to the patient. It is a pain of strictly psychological origin, not being linked to any metabolic disorder detectable by the usual methods. In these cases, a referral to a psychotherapist (psychoanalyst or clinical psychologist) is necessary, after the patient has been examined by a competent medical board, so that the patient can carry out in-depth analyses and discover the possible 'cause' of the disorder and, by exclusion, determine that it is psychalgia.

Psychoanalysis has already defined, in a coherent manner, that the human *psyche* is formed by a tiny conscious part and a titanic and unconscious part. There are certain traumas that, due to the intensity with which they occur and the painful effects they leave, the brain of the victims themselves tries to block such events from their memory in order to protect the individual and preserve their life with greater dignity. But who knows what exogenous factors can awaken the dormant volcano and the traumas resurface, causing the subject to be affected by symptoms that, in the end, are intended to awaken him to a much larger problem, still unsolved. Hence, clinicians and specialists relate psychogenic pain to obsessive neuroses and psychiatric disorders.

Many studies still need to be carried out, with the aim of clarifying how human thought works and what mechanisms it uses to preserve and maintain the psychic economy, sometimes using subterfuges such as the mnemonic suppression of events that the individual could not bear in a conventional way; however, there comes a time when the brain demands the reestablishment of the order broken by the situation to be discovered, because it was suppressed for the sake of the patient's well-being.

In an attempt to force the individual to seek a solution to the existing and persistent conflict caused by the trauma, the unconscious uses all kinds of messages, one of which is [*almost*] unbearable pain, and its persistence leads patients to take extreme attitudes against themselves, abusing various types of psychotropic substances, precisely because this psychic instance is unaware of the meaning of conscious intensity and its effects are at levels that go beyond human limits.

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